

THE MAIN QUALITIES OF THE SPEECH THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SPEECH, THE APPROPRIATENESS OF THE SPEECH

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ANNOTATION

This article gives information about.

Key words: main quality of the speech, effectiveness of the speech, appropriateness of the speech.

Appropriateness of speech is the ratio of speech - the communicative quality of speech that appears based on the conditions of communication. W. R. - such a choice of means of speech that meets the goals and conditions of the speech, the necessary quality of a good speech consisting of such a choice. W. R. corresponds to the subject of the message, its logical and emotional content, the composition of the audience or readers, informational, educational, aesthetic and other tasks of written or oral presentation. As the most important quality of literate speech, relevance can be considered in three interrelated aspects:

- communicative-situational
- methodical
- personal and psychological

The effectiveness of the speech mainly refers to the teacher's oral speech process and takes into account the mental state that appears when it is received by the students. That is, the teacher-speaker should take students into account, monitor their level of knowledge, even their age, and their mood at the time of the speech, and control how their speech is received by the students. It is not appropriate for teachers with professional knowledge to speak in lively, simple language, and teachers who do not have sufficient knowledge of public speaking should not try to speak in scientific and official language. So, the speaker-teacher is required to act according to the situation and it is his task to try to fully convey any idea he wants to express to the students.

Therefore, the speech should be clear and fluent, grammatically correct, obey the rules of literary pronunciation, and be coherent from beginning to end. Based on such speech, the knowledge learned reaches the heart of the student. Such speech meets the

requirements of cultural speech. For this, the teacher requires constant research and work on himself, philological knowledge and constant speech practice

The main requirement for the appropriateness of speech is that each communicative situation should correspond to its own means of linguistic and emotional expression, in particular, the special structure of speech, certain expressive and evaluative turns, etc.

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